

EDICITNET EVENT PLANNING PACKAGE

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Offline Events

(100+ expected participants)

Process	Timing	Steps
Planning & Preparation	2-3 months before	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Send detailed information about the event to UBER in advance via the survey (as soon as possible, but at least 2 months before). 2. UBER to provide a first draft of EdiCitNet key messages. 3. Organise a meeting with UBER to assess who might attend the event, execute a stakeholder analysis and co-formulate calls to action (“Sign up to the network!”, “Join the marketplace” etc.) and objectives adapted to local requirements and identified stakeholders.
	1-2 months before	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. UBER and partner to co-develop an invitation and communication campaign, based on key messages and interests of identified stakeholders. 2. If you have social media channels or a newsletter, screenshot followers/sign-ups (alternatively, record more detailed analytics within social media channels) before campaigning starts. 3. UBER and partner to execute campaign via all channels. 4. UBER to support registration for event via CMT, Facebook and other tools as applicable. 5. Partner to contact media to inform them about the event and request coverage and/or provide UBER with media contacts so UBER can inform them about the event. 6. Prepare materials. Partners may select from the following EdiCitNet materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rollup ● Bags ● Flyers ● Postcards ● Poster ● QR Code <p>UBER will support by adapting the designs and adding all of the necessary information (incl. EdiCitNet & EU commission logos, funding number, coordinating agency, partner information & key messages) to all of the above formats. Please inform UBER at least 5 weeks before event to allow time for the design process and production of materials.</p>
	1 week before event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Partner to print out consent sheets, evaluation sheets, flyers and newsletter sign-up sheets (as needed) prior to the event.
Monitoring & Execution	During event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure clear communication of calls to action set out prior to the event. 2. Monitor event participation with photos and videos (making sure to obtain participant consent - via consent sheets). 3. Gather more detailed information on attendees via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● distribution of materials (flyers/pencils/apples etc.)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • information collected via evaluation sheets • newsletter sign-up sheets.
Follow-up & Dissemination	After event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitor social media, newsletter and external media with screenshots after event. 2. Assess number of participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • based on official visitor numbers of event • number of flyers/pencils/apples distributed • number of evaluation sheets filled out 3. Hold an internal wrap-up session to discuss: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who attended (Was it a diverse audience?) • What was said (Were the key messages expressed & objectives reached?) • Learnings for future events 4. Upload monitoring information (attendance/evaluation) to Sharepoint. 5. Fill in the template for news (including all necessary links, a detailed description and meaningful images). 6. Gather all communication material (photos, news articles, videos etc) and upload it to this folder on Sharepoint. Please use the following structure to name your document ORGANIZATION_YYYYMMDD_EVENT_FILE e.g.: UBER_20210105_FRIEDRICHSTRASSE_PICTURE1 7. UBER to support partners in editing (where necessary) and sharing this content via all possible channels.

Online Events

(100+ expected participants)

Process	Timing	Steps
Planning & Preparation	2-3 months before event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Send detailed information about the event to UBER in advance via the survey (as soon as possible, but at least 2 months before). 2. UBER to provide a first draft of EdiCitNet key messages. 3. Organise a meeting with UBER to assess who might attend the event, execute a stakeholder analysis and co-formulate calls to action (“Sign up to the network!”, “Join the marketplace” etc.) and objectives adapted to local requirements and identified stakeholders.
	1-2 months before event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. UBER and partner to co-develop an invitation and communication campaign, based on key messages and interests of identified stakeholders. 2. If you have social media channels or a newsletter, screenshot followers/sign-ups (alternatively, record more detailed analytics within social media channels) before campaigning starts. 3. UBER and partner to execute campaign via all channels. 4. UBER to support registration for event via CMT, Facebook and other tools as applicable. Be sure to gather information on who is signing up via online event registration form: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Info on organisation and role. • What would they like to get out of attending the event? • How did they hear about this event? 5. Partner to contact media to inform them about the event and request coverage and/or provide UBER with media contacts so we can inform them about the event. 6. Prepare materials. UBER to provide: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slides with key messages • EdiCitnet templates for presentations • Splash screens for intro & outro with EdiCitNet logo • Zoom links (if necessary, please inform us) • Support as moderator and/or presenter • Contacts to experts within consortium and beyond • Support on how to structure event, how to manage different elements <p>Please inform UBER at least 5 weeks before event to allow time for the design process and production of materials.</p>
Monitoring & execution	During event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure clear communication of calls to action set out prior to the event. 2. Monitor event participation with screenshots and/or recordings (making sure to obtain participant consent via online consent sheets). 3. Gather more detailed information on attendees/impact by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • counting how many sign-ups there are & how many attendees and/or

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • carrying out a short evaluation during/at end of event via an online poll, e.g. Mentimeter. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Monitor interaction during the event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • via chat • Q&A • live polls • interactive sessions (Miro boards, etc.)
Follow-up & Dissemination	After event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Send a thank you email to everyone who signed up, linking to EdiCitNet website. Include a short evaluation survey if necessary (if no evaluation was carried out at the end of the event). 2. Monitor social media & other channels with screenshots. 3. Hold an internal wrap-up session to discuss: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who attended (Was it a diverse audience?) • What was said (Were the key messages expressed & objectives reached?) • Learnings for future events 4 Upload monitoring information (attendance/evaluation) to Sharepoint. 4. Fill in the template for news (including all necessary links, a detailed description and meaningful images). 5. Gather all communication material (photos, news articles, videos etc) and upload it to this folder on Sharepoint. Please use the following structure to name your document ORGANIZATION_YYYYMMDD_EVENT_FILE e.g.: UBER_20210105_FRIEDRICHSTRASSE_PICTURE1 6. UBER to support partners in editing (where necessary) and sharing this content via all possible channels.

Offline Events

(fewer than 100 expected participants)

Process	Timing	Steps
Planning & Preparation	2-3 months before event	Send detailed information about the event to UBER in advance via the survey (as soon as possible, but at least 2 months before).
	1-2 months before event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. UBER and partner to publicise event via all channels. 2. UBER to support registration for event via CMT, Facebook, etc. 3. Prepare materials. Partners may select from the following EdiCitNet materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rollup • Bags • Flyers • Postcards • Poster • QR Code <p>UBER will support by adapting the designs and adding all of the necessary information (incl. EdiCitNet & EU commission logos, funding number, coordinating agency, partner information & key messages) to all of the above formats. Please inform UBER at least 5 weeks before event to allow time for the design process and production of materials.</p>
	1 week before event	Partner to print out consent sheets, evaluation sheets, flyers and newsletter sign-up sheets (as needed) prior to the event.
Monitoring & Execution	During event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure clear communication of calls to action/objectives set out prior to the event. 2. Monitor event participation with photos and videos (making sure to obtain participant consent - via consent sheets). 3. Gather more detailed information on attendees via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • distribution of flyers/pencils/apples, etc. • information collected via evaluation sheets • newsletter sign-up sheets.
Follow-up & Dissemination	After event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assess number of participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • based on official visitor numbers of event • number of flyers/pencils/apples distributed • number of evaluation sheets filled out 2. Hold an internal wrap-up session to discuss: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who attended (Was it a diverse audience?) • What was said (Were the key messages expressed & objectives reached?) • Learnings for future events 3. Upload monitoring info (attendance/evaluation) to Sharepoint. 4. Fill in the template for news (including all necessary links, a detailed description and meaningful images). 5. Gather all communication material (photos, news articles, videos etc) and upload it to to Sharepoint. Please use the following structure to name your document

		<p>ORGANIZATION_YYYYMMDD_EVENT_FILE e.g.: UBER_20210105_FRIEDRICHSTRASSE_PICTURE1</p> <p>6. UBER to support partners in editing (where necessary) and sharing this content via all possible channels.</p>
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	1-2 months before	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. UBER and partner to publicise event via all channels (Newsletter, Social Media, local media, etc.). 2. UBER to support registration for event via CMT, Facebook, etc. Be sure to gather information on who is signing up via online event registration form: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Info on organisation and role. • What would they like to get out of attending the event? • How did they hear about this event? 3. Prepare materials. UBER to provide: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slides with key messages • EdiCitnet templates for presentations • Splash screens for intro & outro with EdiCitNet logo • Zoom links (if necessary, please inform us) • Support as moderator and/or presenter • Contacts to experts within consortium and beyond • Support on how to structure & manage event <p>Please inform UBER at least 5 weeks before event to allow time for the design process and production of materials.</p>
Monitoring & execution	During event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure clear communication of calls to action/objectives. 2. Monitor event participation with screenshots and/or recordings. Make sure to obtain participant consent via consent sheets. 3. Gather more detailed information on attendees/impact by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • counting sign-ups & attendees AND/OR • carrying out a short evaluation during/at end of event via an online poll, e.g. Mentimeter. 4. Monitor interaction during the event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • via chat • Q&A • live polls • interactive sessions (Miro boards, etc.)
Follow-up & Dissemination	After event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Send a thank you email to everyone who signed up, linking to EdiCitNet website. Include a short evaluation survey if necessary (if no evaluation was carried out at the end of the event). 2. Hold an internal wrap-up session to discuss: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who attended (Was it a diverse audience?) • What was said (Were the key messages expressed & objectives reached?) • Learnings for future events 3. Upload all monitoring info (attendance/evaluation) to Sharepoint. 4. Fill in the template for news (including all necessary links, a detailed description and

		<p>meaningful images).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">5. Gather all communication material (photos, news articles, videos etc) and upload it to this folder on Sharepoint. Please use the following structure to name your document ORGANIZATION_YYYYMMDD_EVENT_FILE<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ e.g.: UBER_20210105_FRIEDRICHSTRASSE_PICTURE16. UBER to support partners in editing (where necessary) and sharing this content via all possible channels.
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